

The Influence of Self Control, Financial Attitude, and Lifestyle on Personal Financial Management of Accounting Students at Triatma Mulya University

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ABSTRACT

Personal financial management is an individual's ability to plan and control the use of funds effectively to meet current and future needs. For students, this ability is crucial due to limited income sources. However, many students still experience difficulties in managing their finances, as evidenced by consumptive behavior, uncontrolled spending, and a lack of prioritization of needs. This study aims to examine the influence of self-control, financial attitudes, and lifestyle on the personal financial management of accounting students at Triatma Mulya University. This study used a quantitative approach. The population in this study were 154 accounting students at Triatma Mulya University. The sampling method was purposive sampling. The total sample in this study was 106 respondents. The data analysis technique used was multiple linear regression analysis. Based on the analysis results, it can be concluded that self-control and financial attitudes have a positive effect on personal financial management, while lifestyle has no effect on personal financial management.

KEYWORDS: Personal Financial Management, Self-Control, Financial Attitudes, Lifestyle

I. INTRODUCTION

In an era of globalization and modernization marked by rapid economic and technological development, personal financial management skills are crucial for students (Nugroho & Hidayah, 2025). Rising educational costs and increasingly complex living requirements require students to be able to organize and manage their finances effectively and efficiently. This skill is crucial for students to meet their daily needs without experiencing financial difficulties and to maintain financial stability in the future (Harisatrio & Sofia, 2024).

Current trends indicate that students' financial management practices are still suboptimal. This is reflected in the increasing use of digital financial services, such as paylater, which encourages consumer behavior among the younger generation. According to Investor.id (2025), Generation Z is the group that utilizes online lending (pindar) and paylater services most frequently to meet their financial needs. A 2024 Jakpat survey showed that approximately 55% of Generation Z used paylater for urgent needs, 32% for daily needs, and 26% for bill payments. Furthermore, approximately 34% of Generation Z reported using online loans in the past six months, some of which were used to purchase consumer goods such as premium gadgets (Investor.id, 2025).

Furthermore, this phenomenon is further reinforced by a report from Sapos, which states that the number of PayLater users in Indonesia has reached 17.26 million, dominated by the younger generation, even accompanied by an increasing risk of bad debt due to uncontrolled use (Sapos.co.id, 2026). The ease of access, fast processing, and minimal requirements of digital financial services have led to younger generations tending to use these facilities without thorough financial planning, necessitating the need for personal financial management.

Personal financial management is a person's ability to plan, organize, and control the use of money to meet daily needs and achieve future financial goals (Nugroho & Hidayah, 2025). For students, this skill is crucial, as they are required to use limited financial resources (such as pocket money or part-time income) wisely (Humaira & Sagoro, 2018). However, in reality, many students still experience difficulties in managing their finances, such as uncontrolled spending, lack of savings habits, and difficulty in prioritizing needs. These problems are not only caused by limited income but are also influenced by individual behavioral and psychological factors in dealing with money. Therefore, personal financial management is not only related to financial aspects, but also influenced by self-control, financial attitudes, and lifestyles that students live.

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Theory of Planned Behavior from Ajzen (1991) explains that individual behavior is influenced by intentions formed from attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived self-control. In the context of this research, self-control is a form of attitude because it relates to how a person evaluates and responds to a behavior. In financial management, self-control is seen as how a person views the habit of refraining from unnecessary spending. Students with high self-control typically view thrifty and planned behavior as positive, while consumptive behavior is considered detrimental.

The relationship between self-control and financial management is positive and significant, with the better a person's self-control, the more effective their financial management. Self-control helps a person manage their money wisely, prioritize needs, resist excessive consumption, and maintain discipline in saving and investing.

In the Theory of Planned Behavior, financial attitude is positioned as an attitude because it reflects an individual's assessment of the importance of wise financial management. This attitude influences students' intentions to manage spending, save, and plan for the future. Financial attitude is one factor that plays a role in financial management, reflecting an individual's views and feelings about money and its management (Sari *et al.* 2025). A positive financial attitude will encourage students to be more responsible in managing their personal finances.

Lifestyle reflects an individual's behavioral patterns in daily life, including prioritizing needs and spending money. Students with a consumptive lifestyle tend to allocate spending to wants rather than needs, potentially leading to waste and difficulties in personal financial management. Conversely, a simpler and more planned lifestyle encourages individuals to align spending with their financial capabilities. Thus, lifestyle is a significant factor influencing how students manage their personal finances.

According to Calhoun & Acocella (1990), self-control is defined as the regulation of a person's physical, psychological, and behavioral processes, or a series of processes that shape him or her. Self-control is also the totality of the aspects of the processes that shape an individual's personality, encompassing the processes of physical, psychological, and behavioral regulation.

Prihartono & Asandimitra (2018) state that financial attitude is a psychological perspective on money, demonstrated by the ability to control finances, create financial plans, create budgets, and act appropriately in making financial decisions. Humaira & Sagoro (2018) state that the state of mind, opinions, and assessments of personal finances can shape financial attitudes. Financial attitude can also be defined as the application of financial principles to create and maintain value through sound decision-making and management of financial resources.

According to Laksono & Iskandar (2018), lifestyle is a person's attitude in describing a real problem that is in that

person's mind and tends to combine various things related to psychological and emotional problems or can also be seen from what is of interest and his opinion about an object.

Financial management is influenced by several factors, including self-control, financial attitudes, and lifestyle. Good self-control helps students curb unnecessary spending, leading to more organized finances. A positive financial attitude encourages frugality, financial planning, and responsible use of money. Furthermore, lifestyle also influences financial management: a consumptive lifestyle can lead to excessive spending, while a modest lifestyle supports better financial management.

Previous research by Mustikasari & Septina (2023) showed that self-control variables had a positive and significant impact on personal financial management. Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis conducted in this study, research by Artha & Wibowo (2023) found that financial attitudes had a significant partial effect on personal financial management. This means that the more prudent students' financial attitudes are, the better their level of personal financial management will be.

According to Riana & Kristianto (2025), the results of this study indicate that lifestyle does not significantly influence financial management behavior. In contrast, research by Buderini *et al.* (2023) shows that lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on the personal financial management skills of Generation Z students. Research by Nugroho & Hidayah (2025) shows that lifestyle has a significant effect on student financial management.

This study aims to analyze the influence of self-control, financial attitudes, and lifestyle on the personal financial management of accounting students at Triatma Mulya University based on the differences in the results of previous research and the phenomena that occur in current students.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

A. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), introduced by Ajzen (1991), explains that individual behavior is influenced by attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioral control. This theory assumes that individuals act rationally by considering information, experience, and the consequences of their behavior. According to Ajzen (1991), a person's intention to behave is influenced by beliefs about the behavior, social pressure, and the individual's ability to control their actions (Wirawan *et al.* 2022). The TPB has three main components: attitudes toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Hartono, 2007; Marco & Arifin, 2024). In this study, the TPB was used to explain that students' personal financial management behavior is influenced by internal factors such as self-control, financial attitudes, and lifestyle. Students with good self-control and financial attitudes tend to manage their

finances more wisely, while a consumptive lifestyle can influence students' personal financial management behavior.

B. Self-Control on Personal Financial Management

Self-control is an individual's ability to direct thoughts, emotions, and actions toward long-term goals by resisting momentary impulses that can be detrimental to themselves (Tangney *et al.* 2024). In the context of college students, self-control plays a crucial role in regulating excessive consumption behavior and maintaining personal financial balance. According to the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), A person's behavior is influenced by their intentions and perceived behavioral control. College students with high self-control are better able to resist excessive shopping urges and manage expenses according to needs. Research conducted by Rosa & Listiadi (2020) states that self-control has a significant partial effect on college students' personal financial management. This contrasts with research by Mustikasari & Septina (2023), which demonstrated that self-control has a positive and significant effect on personal financial management. Therefore, the proposed hypothesis is:

H1: Self-control has a positive effect on personal financial management.

C. Financial Attitudes towards Personal Financial Management

Financial attitudes are psychological tendencies expressed when evaluating suggested financial management practices based on varying degrees of agreement and disagreement (Humaira & Sagoro, 2018). Financial attitudes can help individuals determine behaviors related to financial management, personal financial planning, or how individuals make investment decisions (Lestari & Amirusholihin, 2026). Financial attitudes relate to a person's financial responsibility regarding how they manage their finances (Meida & Kartini, 2023). According to Ajzen (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior, financial attitudes influence students' intentions to manage their personal finances. Poor financial attitudes can negatively impact financial management, while positive financial attitudes encourage better financial planning (Kusumaningrum *et al.* 2023). Research by Pratita & Martono (2024) also shows that financial attitudes significantly influence students' personal financial management. Based on the description above, the hypothesis that can be put forward is:

H2: Financial attitudes have a positive influence on personal financial management.

D. Lifestyle on Personal Financial Management

Lifestyle is a behavior that reflects how individuals, especially students, socialize and adapt through their appearance and lifestyle. Lifestyle is dynamic and can change over time according to each individual's needs and life goals (Pulungan & Febriaty, 2018). Lifestyle also

reflects how a person allocates funds, time, and lifestyle. According to Normawati *et al.* (2022), lifestyle reflects changes in individual attitudes due to developing trends, which often encourage consumptive behavior and excessive spending. Kartawinata *et al.* (2021) added that a good lifestyle can encourage individuals to be wiser in managing their finances, by adjusting lifestyle expenses to their income. According to Ajzen (1991), Theory of Planned Behavior, lifestyle influences a person's attitude toward financial management (Fadhilah, 2022). Students with a non-consumptive lifestyle tend to be wiser in spending money and are better able to manage their finances (Noviani, 2021). Research by Buderini *et al.* (2023) also shows that lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on personal financial management among Generation Z students. Based on this description, the hypothesis in this study is formulated as follows:

H3: Lifestyle has a positive influence on personal financial management.

E. Research Model

The research model is shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Research Model

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted at Triatma Mulya University. This research location was chosen due to the limited research related to personal financial management. The population in this study were all 154 accounting students at Triatma Mulya University. The sampling method used was purposive sampling, with a total of 106 observations. This study used a questionnaire for data collection with a four-point Likert scale and distributed via Google Form. The data analysis technique used was multiple linear regression analysis. This study used personal financial management as the dependent variable. The independent variables were self-control, financial attitudes, and lifestyle.

The personal financial management measurement indicators from Mustikasari & Septina (2023) are as follows: (1) behavioral control, (2) wasteful behavior, (3) saving behavior, (4) spending. The self-control measurement indicators from Mustikasari & Septina (2023) are as follows: (1) ability to control behavior, (2) ability to make decisions,

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(3) ability to control emotions in spending, (4) controlling impulses to buy unnecessary items. Financial attitude indicators from Ta'dung et al. (2023) include: (1) saving regularly and routinely, (2) writing a budget plan, (3) being responsible for oneself, (4) and financial planning. The measurement of indicators that influence lifestyle from Novitasari et al. (2021) are: (1) activities (2) interests, (3) opinions.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results

A. Descriptive Statistical Test

Table 1. Results of Descriptive Statistical Test

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
X1	106	6,00	20,00	14,7264	1,78637
X2	106	5,00	20,00	16,0472	2,04419
X3	106	5,00	20,00	14,0189	2,51843
Y	106	7,00	20,00	15,3019	1,81617

Source: Processed data (2026)

Descriptive statistics show that the self-control variable has a mean value of 14.7264 with an average score of 2.95 which is included in the "Agree" category, thus indicating that the level of self-control of respondents is classified as good. The financial attitude variable has a mean value of 16.0472 with an average score of 3.21 which is included in the "Agree" category, indicating that respondents have a positive financial attitude. Furthermore, the lifestyle variable has a mean value of 14.0189 with an average score of 2.80 which is included in the "Agree" category, thus indicating that respondents are quite capable of adjusting their lifestyle to their financial conditions. Meanwhile, the personal financial management variable has a mean value of 15.3019 with an average score of 3.06 which is included in the "Agree" category, indicating that respondents have good personal financial management skills.

The research instruments passed the validity and reliability tests. Hypothesis testing was conducted using multiple linear regression analysis, which had previously been validated based on classical assumptions. The results of the normality test using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed a significance value of 0,200, indicating a normal data distribution. The results of the multicollinearity test showed a tolerance value greater than 0.10 and a variance inflation factor less than 10, indicating the absence of multicollinearity. This regression model also showed no signs of heteroscedasticity.

B. Model Feasibility Test Results (F-Test)

Table 2. Results of F-Test

ANOVA ^a						
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	171,555	3	57,185	33,372	0,001 ^b
	Residual	174,785	102	1,714		
	Total	346,340	105			

a. Dependent Variable: Y
b. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X2, X1

Source: Processed data (2026)

The F-value is 33.372 with a significance level of 0.001 < 0.05. These results indicate that this research model is suitable for predicting personal financial management.

C. Coefficient of Determination Test (R2)

Table 3. Results of R2 Test

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0,704 ^a	0,495	0,480	1,30904

a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X2, X1
b. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: Processed data (2026)

The Adjusted R Square value was 0.480, or 48%. This result means that 48% of personal financial management can be explained by self-control, financial attitudes, and lifestyle, while the remaining 52% is influenced by other factors not included in the research model.

D. Hypothesis Test (t-test)

Table 4. Results of the t-test

Variable.	Coef.	t-Statistic.	Sig.	Prediction
X1	0,358	4,079	0,001**	H1(+)
X2	0,393	5,340	0,001**	H2(+)
X3	0,028	0,521	0,603	H3
Constant	3,325	2,607	0,011	
N	106			

** Sig. on level 0,05 (p<0,05)

Source: Processed data (2026)

The self-control test showed a significance value of 0.001, thus supporting H1. The financial attitude test showed a significance value of 0.001, thus supporting H2. Meanwhile, the lifestyle test showed a significance value of 0.603, indicating that the results did not support H3.

Discussions

A. The Influence of Self-Control on Personal Financial Management

The first hypothesis states that self-control has a positive effect on personal financial management. The self-control variable has a regression coefficient of 0.358, and a significance value of 0.001, which is less than 0.05. The results indicate that self-control has a positive effect on

personal financial management among accounting students at Triatma Mulya University, thus H1 is accepted. These results indicate that higher self-control will improve personal financial management.

Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), self-control is related to perceived behavioral control, which is the extent to which an individual is able to control and direct their behavior in decision-making (Ajzen, 1991). The higher an individual's ability to control themselves, the greater their ability to manage their finances rationally and in a planned manner (Aprillia et al. 2024). When someone has strong self-control, they will more easily form positive intentions and direct them towards responsible financial behavior (Amalia & Yuliati, 2025). Students who have good self-control tend to be able to resist consumptive urges, prioritize needs over wants, and consistently maintain financial discipline. This condition encourages the formation of wiser and more directed financial behavior (Oktavianti et al. 2025). Thus, students with high self-control will be more able to manage their personal finances effectively because they have strong control over their financial behavior (Rahmi & Nurhayati, 2025).

The results of this study are in line with the research of Rahmi & Nurhayati (2025), Amalia & Yuliati (2025), Oktavianti et al. (2025), Gunawan & Herlina (2025), Novitasari et al. (2025), Hutami et al. (2025), Aprillia et al. (2024), Sriyani et al. (2024), Mustikasari & Septina (2023), Deccasari et al. (2023), Ekofani & Paramita (2023), Putriasih & Yasa (2022), which showed that self-control has a positive effect on personal financial management. However, these results are not in line with the research of Marissa et al. (2025), Nurjanah et al. (2024), which showed that self-control has no effect on personal financial management.

B. The Influence of Financial Attitudes on Personal Financial Management

The second hypothesis states that financial attitudes have a positive effect on personal financial management. The financial attitudes variable has a regression coefficient of 0.393 and a significance value of 0.001, which is smaller than 0.05. The results indicate that financial attitudes have a positive effect on personal financial management among accounting students at Triatma Mulya University, thus H2 is accepted. These results indicate that better financial attitudes will improve personal financial management.

Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), financial attitudes are related to attitudes toward behavior, namely an individual's assessment of a behavior that will influence the tendency to act (Ajzen, 1991). The more positive an individual's attitude toward financial management, the greater the motivation to implement responsible financial behavior (Novitasari et al. 2025). Students with positive financial attitudes tend to view

saving, financial planning, and spending control as important, thus encouraging the formation of healthy financial habits (Abdillah et al. 2025). This condition strengthens the individual's commitment to managing finances effectively and sustainably. Thus, students with positive financial attitudes will be better able to manage their personal finances because they are driven by good judgment and belief in the importance of financial management (Florensa et al. 2024).

The results of this study are in line with those of Novitasari et al. (2025), Pratita & Martono (2024), Abdillah et al. (2025), Florensa et al. (2024), Laif & Putra (2024), Artha & Wibowo (2023), which stated that financial attitudes have a positive effect on personal financial management. The results of this study are not in line with those of Marissa et al. (2025), Ekofani & Paramita (2023), Dyansyah & Pandin (2024), Irawati & Kasemetan (2023), Wahyuni et al. (2023), which stated that financial attitudes have no effect on personal financial management.

C. The Influence of Lifestyle on Personal Financial Management

The third hypothesis states that lifestyle has a positive effect on personal financial management. The lifestyle variable has a regression coefficient of 0.028 and a significance value of 0.603, which is greater than 0.05. The results indicate that lifestyle has no effect on financial management among accounting students at Triatma Mulya University, thus rejecting H3. This means that lifestyle has no effect on personal financial management.

Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), lifestyle is related to subjective norms, namely the influence of the social environment on individual behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Theoretically, the higher an individual's tendency to follow a certain lifestyle, the more it can influence financial behavior (Deccasari et al. 2023). However, the results of this study indicate that lifestyle does not influence personal financial management. Students do not consider lifestyle as a primary factor in managing their finances. Students tend to adjust their expenses to their limited financial capabilities (Maulana et al. 2025). Students still consider internal factors such as self-control and financial attitudes more. Students have rational and selective considerations in following trends, so lifestyle is not a primary factor in personal financial management. Thus, a high or low lifestyle does not determine the quality of students' personal financial management (Wati et al. 2025).

The results of this study align with those of Mardianto et al. (2024), Putri & Padang (2025), Aziz et al. (2025), Maulana et al. (2025), Wati et al. (2025), which showed that lifestyle had no effect on personal financial management. However, these results are inconsistent with those of Deccasari et al. (2023), Ekofani & Paramita (2023), Putriasih & Yasa (2022), Laif & Putra (2024), Liwanto &

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Setyani (2024), which showed that lifestyle had a positive effect on personal financial management.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to analyze the factors influencing personal financial management of accounting students at Triatma Mulya University by examining the influence of self-control, financial attitudes, and lifestyle on personal financial management of accounting students at Triatma Mulya University. The research sample consisted of 106 respondents who were accounting students from Triatma Mulya University who met the research sample criteria, namely active students in the accounting study program and had taken financial management courses. Based on the results of the analysis and discussion, it can be concluded:

1. Self-control has a positive impact on personal financial management. This means that the greater the self-control, the better your personal financial management.
2. Financial attitudes have a positive impact on personal financial management. This means that better financial attitudes will improve personal financial management.
3. Lifestyle has no impact on personal financial management. This means that a high or low lifestyle is not a determining factor in personal financial management.

LIMITATION

A limitation of this study is that it only involved accounting students at Triatma Mulya University as respondents, so the results cannot be generalized widely. Furthermore, the Adjusted R Square value of 0.480 indicates that personal financial management can only be explained by 48% of self-control, financial attitudes, and lifestyle, while the remaining 52% is influenced by other factors outside the research model.

SUGGESTION

Further research can expand the scope of the study by involving respondents from different regions or groups and adding other independent variables, such as financial literacy, income, and family environment, which can influence students' personal financial management.

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